

MELATONIN: A BETTER CANCER TREATMENT OPTION

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Abstract: Cancer is a group of diseases which is characterized by uncontrolled proliferation of cells and their invasion to nearby tissues from primary ones, and formation of secondary tumor mass by the process called metastasis. Its prevalence is worldwide. Cancer cells having some properties which poses difficulty in cancer treatment include dysregulated metabolism, genomic instability, immune avoidance, increased telomerase activity resulting resistant to most of the cancer treatments. Cancer treatment requires expensive therapies such as chemotherapy and radiotherapy. Such treatments generally lead to several side effects therefore there is a need of other alternative, effective and less expensive treatment options. One of such option is melatonin which plays an important role in circadian rhythm regulation. An extensive study on melatonin shows that it can be used as an anti-cancer agent. In this review, the main aim is to provide a brief overview about the role of melatonin in alleviation of cancer initiation, progression and metastasis. The emphasis has been given to the studies where melatonin and its metabolites have been used in a concentration dependent manner in preclinical (in vitro as well as in vivo) studies.

Keywords: cancer, dysregulated metabolism, metastasis, angiogenesis, apoptosis, melatonin.

1. INTRODUCTION

Cancer is the second leading cause of death or mortality worldwide after ischemic heart diseases. According to International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC), cancer is responsible for about 9.6 million deaths in 2018 only. It is estimated that about 1 in 6 deaths globally is because of cancer. Some behavioral and dietary factors contributes to cancer initiation which include excessive use of tobacco and alcohol, high body mass, low intake of antioxidant rich fruits and vegetables, sedentary work etc. Another group of carcinogenic factors includes hepatitis, human papilloma virus, Epstein-Barr virus, some bacteria for instance *Helicobacter pylori* are responsible for cancer deaths (Parkin, 2006). Other genetic factors such as dysfunction in cell cycle genes and unavailability or reduced expression of tumor suppressor genes lead to abnormalities in cell proliferation and uncontrolled cell divisions which is an essential property of cancer cells (Matlashewski *et al.*, 1984; Seto *et al.*, 2010).

Some alterations in gene expression may results in cancer. Epigenetics is a dynamic process and is characterized by a group of modifications such as DNA methylation, histone protein modification and nucleosome positioning which ultimately affects the gene expression (Alvarez-Buylla *et al.*, 2008; Portela and Esteller, 2010). Hypomethylated DNA is characteristic feature of cancer cells and its responsible factor for cancer initiation. According to National Cancer Institute (NCI), USA, current cancer treatments includes surgery, radiation therapy, chemotherapy, stem cell transplant, targeted therapy, hormone therapy, immunotherapy and precision medicine. NCI state that various side effects also associated with cancer treatment including loss of appetite, constipation, thrombocytopenia, alopecia, sleep problems, lymphedema, fertility issues, memory problems, peripheral neuropathy etc.

Cancer is not a static disease but it continues to spread all over the body by forming secondary tumor mass. The seriousness of this disease is also reflected by its characteristics which are different among different types of cells. Some medications are applicable for one type of cancer but not for others. This difference in the treatment efficacy may be due to the fact that advanced stages of cancer are more resistant to the cancer treatment. By reviewing this literature from previous research work and review articles, it was observed that melatonin has a

great potential to inhibit cancer initiation, progression and metastasis. This neurohormone may be used in cancer treatment because it helps to overcome conventional cancer treatment and associated side effects.

Melatonin shows inhibitory effects on various cancer cell properties such as genomic instability, uncontrolled proliferation, dysregulated metabolism, replicative immortality and so on. In one experiment, it was found that melatonin inhibited telomerase activity in MCF-7 cells xenograft transplanted on nude mice under laboratory conditions (Leon-Blanco *et al.*, 2003). Estrogen receptor signaling is responsible for uncontrolled proliferation of mammary cancer cells. Melatonin binds to estrogen receptors (ERs) and inhibits their stimulation (Gonzalez, 2005). Some factors like hypoxia inducible factor-1 (HIF-1) during hypoxic condition can induce gene transcription that lead to the activation of certain protein kinases which are responsible for dysregulated metabolism. Melatonin has inhibitory effects on HIF-1 that results in the inhibition of cancer cell metabolism (Vaupel and Meyer, 2007). The replicative immortality of cancer cells can be inhibited by repressing various targets like mTOR (mammalian target of rapamycin), CDK4/6, PI3K (phosphoinositide 3-kinase) and Akt (Block *et al.*, 2015).

2. Melatonin (Hormone of the night)

Current research on pineal gland can be traced back to the great discovery of melatonin by Arnon B. Lerner, a dermatologist who made this advance in 1958 (Lerner *et al.*, 1959). Melatonin (N-acetyl-5-methoxytryptamine) is a neurohormone derived from tryptophan and produced by the pineal gland, intestinal epithelium, retina, skin, bone marrow and in mitochondria, in response to darkness (Bertrand *et al.*, 2014; Tan *et al.*, 2016; Slominski *et al.*, 2018). This hormone is known for its role in circadian rhythms (Hardeland *et al.*, 2011). Melatonin has many important functions like anti-inflammatory, immunomodulatory, vasoregulatory, and antioxidant properties (Montilla *et al.*, 2001; Bonnefont-Rousselot and Collin, 2010). Melatonin can act by binding to cell membrane receptors MT1, MT2, and also by its cytoplasmic receptors, MT3/QR2 (Dubocovich and Markowska, 2005; Jockers *et al.*, 2008). The anti-cancer effects of melatonin can be either receptor-dependent or receptor-independent. In the former case these receptors are involved in inhibiting uptake of linoleic acid, which leads to the downregulation of various key proteins involved in cancer cell proliferation while in the latter case it was found that melatonin directly induce apoptosis, inhibits angiogenesis and cancer metabolism (Sainz *et al.*, 2003; Srinivasan *et al.*, 2008; Hill *et al.*, 2015).

2.1 Chemical properties of melatonin

The hydrophobicity of melatonin is of physiological importance as it facilitates the rapid transition of this molecule across membranes. Thus, newly synthesized melatonin rapidly released from the pinealocytes. Melatonin is transferred to the developing fetus in the womb via placenta and to the newborn child through milk. The hydrophobic characteristic of melatonin is also important as it is the basis of melatonin extraction for analytical studies with the help of chromatography techniques. The biological specificity of this molecule is due to two moieties, N-acetyl group and the O-methyl group (Figure.1) (Sugden *et al.*, 2004; Dubocovich *et al.*, 2010). Melatonin receptors (MT1/MT2) belong to the G-protein coupled receptor (GPCR) family. The affinity of these receptors for melatonin derivatives shows variability. 2-iodomelatonin have highest affinity for these receptors in comparison to other derivatives (Vakkuri *et al.*, 1984). Melatonin derivative such as 2-iodomelatonin is used in radioimmunoassay to measuring melatonin levels, used to localize receptors histologically and to analyze binding affinity (Zlotos *et al.*, 2014). MT3 is a cytoplasmic receptor and its activation leads to melatonin dependent cytotoxicity as well as apoptosis of the cancer cells. (Pariante *et al.*, 2017).

Figure.1 Structure of melatonin.

(Source:pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/melatonin)

2.2 Melatonin synthesis and metabolism

The pineal gland is the major site for melatonin production due to external stimuli (darkness) and acts as a melatonin factory. Specifically, pinealocytes of pineal gland are responsible for melatonin synthesis and responsible for most of the melatonin concentration in blood circulation of mammals (Oksche, 1984; Collin *et al.*, 1989). Pinealocytes can be identified by using histological techniques to stain the proteins which take part in phototransduction process. The category of proteins, one out of which is protein S-antigen which is expressed in retina and pineal gland, plays an important role in phototransduction in retina and some other signal transduction in pineal gland such as neurochemical signal transduction. (Korf *et al.*, 1985; Van Veen *et al.*, 1986; Lolley *et al.*, 1992). During synthesis, tryptophan is converted into 5-hydroxytryptophan in the presence of enzyme tryptophan hydroxylase. Then decarboxylation occurs that convert 5-hydroxytryptophan into 5-hydroxytryptamine. The synthesis of melatonin is regulated by an important enzyme, Arylalkylamine-N-acetyltransferase (AANAT), also known as *timezyme*. This enzyme is involved in the conversion of serotonin to N-acetyl-5-hydroxytryptamine. Hydroxyindole-O-methyltransferase can convert N-acetyl-5-hydroxytryptamine into melatonin and in next step hydroxylation of melatonin occurred by the enzyme cytochrome P450 mono-oxygenases. The further steps leads to the conjugation of product with sulphate that results in the production of 6-sulphatoxymelatonin (Figure.2) (Claustrat *et al.*, 2005).

Figure.2 Synthesis and metabolism of melatonin.

3. Action of Melatonin against cancer

At three main successive stages of cancer, melatonin shows different effects. During initiation, melatonin triggers apoptosis in cancer cells. At progression stage of cancer, melatonin inhibits dysregulated metabolism. During the metastasis stage, melatonin inhibits epithelial-mesenchymal transition.

3.1 Enhancing pro-apoptotic protein activity

The anti-apoptotic protein molecules like Bcl-2 play a pivotal role in apoptosis resistance of cancer cells. By downregulating the expression of anti-apoptotic proteins and enhancing pro-apoptotic protein activity, melatonin induce apoptosis in cancer cells. It has been used for the treatment of pancreatic cancer by downregulation of the expression of Bcl-2 and upregulation of Bax, and caspase-3 expression thus causing the induction of apoptosis (Xu *et al.*, 2013). The apoptosis in cancer cells after melatonin administration was also reported in other cancer types including human hepatoma (Fan *et al.*, 2010) and murine gastric cancer (Xu *et al.*, 2014). It also increases the reactive oxygen species (ROS) level in cancer cells to toxic levels. Another group of proteins, histone deacetylase are involved in the removal of acetyl group from histone tails. Various HDAC enzymes are found in upregulated form in cancer cells. Melatonin downregulates the expression of HDAC-1 and induce apoptosis in non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) (Zhiqiang *et al.*, 2016).

3.2 Control on dysregulated metabolism

Melatonin when binds to its receptors (MT1 and MT2), the α -subunit from the G-protein, attached to the cytoplasmic side, dissociates and inhibit the adenylate cyclase enzyme which is then responsible for the inhibition of ATP (Adenosine triphosphate) and cAMP (Cyclic Adenosine monophosphate) production that is followed by decrease in linoleic acid (LA) uptake thereby reducing LA metabolism to 13-Hydroxy octadecadienoic acid (13-HODE) and ultimately inhibits cancer progression (Jung and Ahmad, 2006).

3.3 Inhibition of angiogenesis

The dividing cancer cells require oxygen and essential nutrients that are required to sustain cell division (Folkman, 1995). The formation of blood vessels or angiogenesis is an important process for cancer development and progression. The anti-angiogenic effects of melatonin has been observed in various studies. In renal adenocarcinoma mouse model, after treatment with melatonin, the disruption of blood vessel formation around tumor mass was observed (Kim *et al.*, 2013). One study showed that the oral administration of melatonin downregulates the expression of serum vascular epithelial growth factor (VEGF) (Lissoni *et al.*, 2001). Melatonin also showed inhibitory effects on VEGF in MCF-7 cells and glioblastoma cells (Alvarez-García *et al.*, 2013; Zhang *et al.*, 2013).

3.4 Inhibition of tissue invasion and metastasis

Cancer metastasis requires disruption of cell-cell adhesion that leads to tissue invasion. This process continues with transfer of cancer cells to nearby sites and results in the formation of secondary tumor (Gupta and Massague, 2006). Cancer cells mainly disrupt the cell-cell adhesion, and become capable to leave the primary tissue and to invade the nearby tissues. Melatonin has inhibitory effect on the invasion of cancer cells. It alters the expression of cell-cell adhesion proteins. E-cadherin and occludin have an important role in tight junctions and low expression of E-cadherin has been observed in the metastatic cancer cells (Beavon, 2000). A study on breast cancer cells showed that melatonin treatment increases expression of E-cadherin and β 1-integrin (Cos *et al.*, 1998). Some proteins through extensive remodeling of extracellular matrix (ECM) helps in cancer cell migration. The matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs) are involved in remodeling of ECM, these enzymes release some biochemical signals that increases cancer cell dissemination. Melatonin has been demonstrated to modulate the expression levels of MMPs (Swarnakar *et al.*, 2009). The enzymatic activity of MMP-9 is repressed by melatonin through binding to its active site directly and it was reported in gastric adenocarcinoma cell line (Rudra *et al.*, 2013). Cancer cells break contact with their nearby attached cells and migrate to other site during epithelial mesenchymal transition (EMT) (Su *et al.*, 2017). Melatonin prevent NF- κ B signaling pathway thereby inhibit EMT (Jardim-Perassi *et al.*,

2014). Vimentin is a protein involved in preservation of mesenchymal phenotype and help in cell invasion (Lilienbaum and Paulin, 1993). A decreased expression of vimentin and inhibition of cell invasion was reported in cancer cells treated with melatonin (Goncalves *et al.*, 2014). Figure.3 summarizes the action of melatonin against cancer.

Figure.3 Action of Melatonin against Cancer.

4. Melatonin making cancer cells more sensitive for treatment

The role of steroid hormone, estrogen in mammary cancer cell proliferation is very well known. It may initiate mammary cell proliferation through the stimulation or activation of ERs. Several *in vitro* studies have shown that MCF-7 cells containing ER- α become sensitive to cancer therapies if melatonin is also added to culture medium (Wilson *et al.*, 1992). Dauchy *et al.* (2014) tested whether or not the low melatonin level contributed to the resistance of cancer to conventional cancer therapies. They selected drug tamoxifen and implanted MCF-7 cells with ER α in thymectomized nude rats. The animal model was placed in 12 hours period of light and 12 hours period of night. Alteration were added by providing complete dark night or with low intensity light exposure at night, that significantly restrained the increase in melatonin level during night. When low intensity light exposed rats were given tamoxifen, then the tumor cells were resistance to drug therapy and continued to grow. On the other hand, in those rat which were kept under a period of 12 hours light and 12 hours darkness, the tamoxifen treatment regressed the tumor growth more quickly. They concluded that the nighttime suppression of melatonin due to low intensity of light was likely the reason for minimizing the responsiveness of tumors to tamoxifen treatment. The disturbance in circadian rhythm was the contributing factor in tamoxifen resistance. The low intensity light during night enhanced the initiation of tumors more frequently in contrast with rats exposed to complete darkness at night (Dauchy *et al.*, 1999; Blask *et al.*, 2011).

Melatonin elicits complex pleiotropic effects on cancer cells. It kills cancer cells smartly and may be considered as a “Smart Killer”. It triggers pro-apoptotic processes in cancer cells while in normal cells it works oppositely and thereby modulates anti-apoptotic signaling. Melatonin improved the anti-cancer therapy when it was used as a co-treatment. The action of melatonin showed specificity in some findings as it promotes damage in cancer cells but protecting normal cells from damage. (Bizzarri *et al.*, 2013).

Table. Evidence of melatonin action on hormone-dependent as well as hormone-independent cancer.

Sr. No.	Type of Cancer	Study Type	Dose	Melatonin action	References
1.	Mammary Adenocarcinoma (rats)	<i>in vivo</i>	2.5mg/kg	Suppression of prolactin level	Tamarkin <i>et al.</i> , 1981
2.	Breast cancer (MDA-MB-361)	<i>in vitro</i>	1mM	Inhibiting cell proliferation and induction of apoptosis.	Wang <i>et al.</i> , 2012
3.	Pancreatic cancer (AR42J cells)	<i>in vitro</i>	1mM	Reducing the cell viability by activating caspase-3.	Gonzalez <i>et al.</i> , 2011
4.	Leukemia (rats)	<i>in vivo</i>	20 μ g/ml	Anti-apoptotic effects on lymphocytes and neutrophils.	Delgado <i>et al.</i> , 2011
5.	Leiomyosarcoma (nude rats)	<i>in vivo</i>	Human melatonin rich blood	Inhibiting tumor proliferation by suppressing survival signaling.	Mao <i>et al.</i> , 2016
6.	Lung Cancer (A549 cells)	<i>in vitro</i>	1mM, 2.5mM and 5mM	Inhibiting cancer cell migration and viability.	Zhou <i>et al.</i> , 2014
7.	Cervical cancer (nude rats)	<i>in vivo</i>	500pM	Inhibiting tumor growth by inhibiting fatty acid metabolic signaling.	Dauchy <i>et al.</i> , 2013
8.	Ovarian cancer (rats)	<i>in vivo</i>	200 μ g/100g	Reduction of tumor mass by	Chuffa <i>et al.</i> , 2016

				inducing apoptosis.	
9.	Prostate cancer (mice)	<i>in vivo</i>	4Nm	Reduction tumor growth by inhibiting angiogenesis.	Paroni <i>et al.</i> , 2014
10.	Breast cancer (rats)	<i>in vivo</i>	Melatonin rich blood from human	Affecting tumor invasion by activating GSK β	Mao <i>et al.</i> , 2012
11.	Prostate cancer (LNCaP cells)	<i>in vitro</i>	1mM	Induce apoptosis in cancer cell by sensitizing them to cytokines.	Rodriguez-Garcia <i>et al.</i> , 2013

Conclusion:

This review brings information about the use of melatonin as an anti-cancer agent. A neurohormone which is necessary for the regulation of circadian rhythm and whose role in alleviation of cancer has been reported in many clinical and experimental studies. Extensive studies have shown that melatonin alleviates cancer at different stage. It is responsible for the production of high oxidative stress in cancer cells. Many anticancer drugs along with melatonin, kill cancer cells by increasing reactive oxygen species (ROS) to toxic level.

Other cancer hallmarks that relates to uncontrolled cell proliferation were observed in cancer cells. Many studies have proved that melatonin show pro-apoptotic effects against many cancer types. It downregulates the production of some key molecules that are associated with cancer cell proliferation such as HIF-1. It inhibits transcriptional activity of some lipid kinases, CDKs, cyclins, and various growth factors that are involved in cancer cell proliferation. Treatment of melatonin has been found to control various angiogenic factors. EMT is a pivotal step for cancer cell metastasis. After melatonin administration the downregulated expression of proteins involved in EMT can be seen.

Differences in incubation conditions and treatment duration of melatonin has different effects for different cancer cell lines and xenografts. Melatonin acts on specific cells via its receptors. The signaling pathways finally leads to inhibition of cancer cell growth and development. Various studies show that melatonin is less toxic when compared to other chemicals used for the treatment of cancer. Melatonin control cellular mechanisms directly or indirectly and leads to the activation or inactivation of genes. Melatonin is very useful for cancer treatment as many scientists have proved its efficacy. The clinical trials must be increased to understand the underlying principles of melatonin action. It inhibits cancer initiation. It is responsible for the inhibition of cancer progression by downregulating key molecules involved in cancer cell proliferation. It also downregulates the expression of those proteins which are involved in tumor invasion and metastasis. It makes cancer cells more sensitive for treatment. This makes melatonin an important anticancer therapeutic. More clinical and experimental studies are required to prove melatonin as a therapeutic option for human use to treat cancer. It is likely possible that melatonin may inhibit the cancer in human. Future research is required to gather more information to understand about its detailed mechanism of action.

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